

INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF MSMEs IN THE ERA OF REVOLUTION 5.0 AT MAKASSAR CITY

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Abstract

This study focuses on the influence of entrepreneurial and market orientation on the competitive advantage of creative industry MSMEs in Makassar City in the Industrial Revolution 5.0 era. The urgency of this study is based on the urgent need to understand the key factors that can increase the competitiveness of MSMEs in facing challenges and opportunities arising from technological developments and rapid market changes. The Revolution 5.0 era emphasizes integrating advanced technology with human aspects, so it is important for MSMEs to adapt and innovate to remain relevant and competitive. The main objective of this study is to identify and analyses how entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation can drive the competitive advantage of creative industry MSMEs. This study will explore the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and innovation and flexibility of MSMEs. The influence of market orientation on the ability of MSMEs to understand and respond to customer needs and preferences. The interaction between entrepreneurial and market orientation creates effective strategies to achieve competitive advantage.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial orientation; Marketing digitalization; Creative industry; Industrial revolution 5.0.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing the competitiveness of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the industrial revolution 5.0 era in Makassar City is a challenge as well as an important opportunity to pay attention to (Azis et al, 2023). The Industrial Revolution 5.0, which emphasizes collaboration between humans and advanced technology, opens up various possibilities for MSMEs to improve efficiency, innovation, and customer service (Adiningsih, 2019).

Several strategies can be carried out to increase the competitiveness of MSMEs in Makassar by utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) and big data analysis to understand market trends, and consumer behaviour, and improve business decisions (Darmasetiawan et al, 2020). With more and more consumers shopping online, MSMEs needs to be present on e-commerce platforms and use digital marketing strategies such as SEO, paid advertising, and social media (Daga et al, 2024).

Product innovation tailored to the needs of local and global consumers can increase the competitiveness of MSMEs (Abduh et al, 2024). Providing personalized and technology-friendly services can increase customer satisfaction. Holding training that focuses on new technologies, business management, and digital skills is essential to improving the competence of MSME human resources (Ruslan et al, 2023).

Collaboration with universities and other educational institutions can help provide relevant and in-depth training for MSME owners and employees. Using fintech platforms to facilitate access to financing, either through online loans, crowdfunding, or other investments (Judijanto et al, 2024). Building relationships with local banks to gain access to credit and financial support. Identifying new market opportunities both domestically and internationally can help MSMEs grow faster. Building a strong brand and effective marketing campaigns will help MSMEs become better known and trusted by consumers.

Collaborating with large companies, governments, and non-profit organizations to expand networks and gain support (Kilay et al, 2022). Joining a business community or MSME association in Makassar to share experiences, knowledge, and resources. Leveraging technology to automate business processes, such as inventory management, accounting, and customer relations. Improving the supply chain and logistics infrastructure to ensure faster and more efficient product distribution (Syahrudin, 2020). By implementing these strategies, MSMEs in Makassar City can increase their competitiveness in the era of the Industrial Revolution 5.0, making them more adaptive, innovative, and able to survive in global competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Potential application of securitization of MSME assets

Credit securitization is a process that allows banks to fund asset growth and in particular eliminate credit risk or reduce pressure on capital ratio obligations. Securitization has been implemented in the United States, Spain, China, Japan, and France to reduce liquidity mismatch problems, increase credit, transfer credit risk to other parties, help the financial sector create investment instrument options, and encourage financial markets to run more efficiently and deeper (Thamrin Abduh, 2018).

The securitization of MSME credit assets in Spain and Japan was motivated by a less-than-optimal monetary transmission mechanism, while in France it was carried out to reduce bank dependence on the Central Bank to fulfill liquidity after the global financial crisis (Wendi et al, 2023).

In France, the Central Bank plays a major role in the process of securitizing MSME credit assets, and securitization is supported by various existing platforms to make the securitization process easier and cheaper, thus becoming an alternative financing for MSMEs (Karim et al, 2023). The platform, namely the French Central Bank (BdF), rates companies in France including SMEs, Credit claims are accepted as collateral by the French Central Bank, and BDF initiated the formation of SPV Euro Secured Notes Issuer (ESNI) in 2012 (Rahman et al, 2018).

Indonesia itself, an important milestone in asset securitization began in 2009 through the securitization of mortgage bills by Bank BTN. However, asset securitization activities have not yet developed due to the limited types of assets, volumes, and market players.

For the success of SME credit asset securitization, it is necessary to select underlying assets because SME credit performance varies by sector, bank type, BUKU bank group, and region (Pasolo et al, 2023). Based on historical data, banks that distribute a lot of SME credit are state-owned banks and national private banks or BUKU 3 and BUKU 4 banks. The NPL of BUKU 4 banks is also the lowest.

The characteristics required for an asset to be used as an ideal underlying asset for securitization are a type of credit that is homogeneous, very safe, has a stable cash flow stream, and has a relatively long term (Bahtiar et al, 2021). Based on the results of the analysis, information was obtained that there is still an imbalance between the demand and supply of SME credit in Indonesia. From the results of the study, there is a projected gap between the demand and supply of SME credit at the end of 2019 IDR 771.86 trillion. In the normal and pessimistic scenarios, the gap is larger, amounting to IDR 1,258 trillion and IDR 1,524 trillion respectively at the end of 2019.

Securitization of SME credit assets is something good and attractive to obtain liquidity, a risk transfer tool, and an alternative in achieving the target portfolio of SME credit distribution (Abduh & Remmang, 2023). However, banks do not yet see securitization of SME credit assets as an urgent need, at least in the short term because. Banks need to study further the securitization of SME credit assets that will be carried out. Banks do not yet have liquidity problems (Karim et al, 2023). Several banks have not been able to meet the target ratio of SME credit. In the future, the need for SME securitization is projected to strengthen, considering the still low distribution of SME credit compared to the total credit needs of the SME sector, as well as the encouragement for banks to have a larger portion of credit distribution to SMEs in the future (Agit et al, 2024).

To encourage the realization of SME credit asset securitization, there are at least two roles that Bank Indonesia can play in the SME credit asset securitization scheme in Indonesia, namely: (1) The first role, Bank Indonesia is involved in the final part of the securitization process, namely playing a role in conducting transactions of securities resulting from SME credit asset securitization (EBA UKM) as securities that are repo-ed to BI in the context of lending facilities (Halik et al, 2023). In addition, it can provide additional incentives in the form of a lower discount rate if the bank uses EBA UKM. Related to the first role, the current PBI and SE BI require that under normal conditions BI limits securities that can be repo-ed to only SBI, SDBI, and SBN.

Meanwhile, the central banks of other countries, such as France, accept various types of financial instruments that can be used as eligible collateral. (2) The second role, Bank Indonesia plays a role in the initial process of securitization through (a) an indirect role in the form of policies and regulations that can encourage the creation of supply and demand for EBA SME products or (b) being directly involved in the preparation and socialization process of securitization of SME credit assets, including encouraging the formation of parties needed in the process of securitization of SME credit assets such as originators who can become pioneers or arrangers/SPVs. In terms of the formation of SPVs or rating agencies, BI needs to coordinate with OJK as the macroprudential authority (Hasniati et al, 2023).

In addition, BI can also play a role through issuing policies within the macroprudential framework, to increase financial access to SMEs and encourage a balanced and quality intermediation function.

2. Society 5.0

Society 5.0 is a concept that originated in Japan and reflects the stages of evolution of society based on the role of technology. We have gone through several previous eras, such as Society 1.0 which focused on agriculture, Society 2.0 which was marked by the Industrial Revolution, Society 3.0 with the internet, and Society 4.0 which integrated artificial intelligence and advanced technology (Juharni et al, 2024).

What sets Society 5.0 apart is its focus on humanity. This is an era where technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and big data are used to improve the quality of human life and solve social problems. It is a combination of high technology and concern for human values (Mardjuni et al, 2022).

In Society 5.0, we can see the use of artificial intelligence in the health sector. Medical robots equipped with AI can assist in complex surgical procedures, increasing accuracy and reducing risks. This technology is not only about efficiency but also about saving lives and improving the quality of life. In addition, Society 5.0 also emphasizes the concept of a “smart city”. These smart cities use technology to manage resources more efficiently, reduce carbon emissions, and provide better public services. In more depth, Society 5.0 is about integrating technology into our lives in a smarter, more humane, and more sustainable way. Here are some key aspects that set this era apart (Nurcahyadi et al, 2023).

Seamless Connection: The Internet of Things (IoT) is at the heart of Society 5.0. It refers to a network of interconnected devices and objects that can communicate intelligently. For example, a smart home that can automatically adjust temperature, lighting, and security based on our preferences and conditions (Suman et al, 2020).

Artificial Intelligence (AI): AI technology is used to make sense of the big data generated by IoT. In the context of healthcare, AI can analyze patient medical data and provide more accurate and faster diagnoses. **Industry 4.0:** Society 5.0 also encompasses the concept of Industry 4.0, which refers to the transformation of the Industrial Revolution through automation, digitization, and data integration. This leads to greater efficiency in production and resource use (Rahmi & Mursyidin, 2024).

The application of technology in urban management is one of the main focuses. This includes intelligent traffic management, efficient energy use, and more sustainable infrastructure. Society 5.0 expects active participation from society (Rosyadah et al, 2021). We are not only consumers of technology but also contribute to the development of solutions to social problems through technology. In education, technology can be used to provide access to quality education for all, regardless of geographic location or economic background.

Society 5.0 is a picture of the future where technology is used to provide solutions to social problems, improve our quality of life, and have a positive impact on society as a whole. For

the younger generation, this is a challenge and an opportunity to play an active role in directing this future journey. Society 5.0 is one of the phases that can provide many relevant changes in people's lives (Sobirin et al, 2024).

The many lives that provide changes are very relevant to everyday life and needs. This is related to the replacement of new professions that correlate with technology (Umiyati & Zeyaya, 2023). The operation of existing systems in human life has a wide set with the comfort of the scope of work to the supply of energy and certainty related to trains that have quite broad relevance in social life.

The operating system supported by Society 5.0 has urgency in terms of people's lives that have been well integrated with technological collaboration. This is also the beginning of forming comfort that has given rise to many people in the eligible era (Karim et al, 2022). The lives of these people are directly related to medical care and transportation to educational life and shopping which are facilitated by technological advances.

Society 5.0 has a more major phase of change than the Industrial Revolution 4.0 stage. This activity lasts quite a long time so the process is known to be longer and difficult to be directly implemented by the community. One of the stages that makes the society 5.0 era have a fairly strong relationship with the emergence of many jobs originating from IT.

This is very dependent on the competence and facilities or means that support these activities can be obtained naturally. IT-based management can be said to be very comfortable and able to provide many innovative breakthroughs to improve capabilities and the economy that are relevant to the needs of other communities (Karim et al, 2021). This stage is also very relevant using the sophistication of AI which is one of the IT devices to facilitate human performance in the society 5.0 era.

METHOD

This study will use two main instruments: interviews and direct observation. Using semi-structured interview guidelines to gain in-depth insights from MSME actors regarding entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation. Interviews will be conducted face-to-face or through digital platforms for convenience and efficiency (Madhavan et al, 2024).

Direct observation in the field to see firsthand how MSME actors apply entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation in their operations. Field notes and documentation photos will be used as part of the data. Data will be collected from MSME actors in the creative industry in Makassar City through questionnaire surveys and in-depth interviews. The survey will be conducted online and offline to achieve wider coverage.

In-depth interviews will be conducted with MSME owners or managers to obtain more detailed and contextual information (Mardjuni & Karim, 2024). The research population is all MSMEs in the creative industry in Makassar City. Samples were taken randomly from as many as 200 MSMEs for quantitative surveys and 20 MSMEs for qualitative interviews. While the indicator variables are as follows:

Research flow diagram

Figure 1: Research framework

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Validity and reliability test results

In this study, validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure the validity and accuracy of the research instruments used. The validity test criteria are to compare the corrected item-total correlation value with the r-table value at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, which is 0.1996 (Ghozali, 2018). If the r-calculated value is greater than the r-table value, then the indicator is considered valid or suitable for use. In addition, a reliability test was also carried out related to the accuracy or consistency of the data. The reliability test uses the alpha coefficient (Cronbach's alpha), with a value of 0.60 as the minimum limit to be considered reliable (Sugiyono, 2011). A variable or construct is said to be reliable if the alpha value is above 0.60. The results of the validity and reliability tests can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Results of validity and reliability tests

Latent construct / variable	Item (indicator)	Corrected item-total correlation	Reliabilities (Cronbach α)
Entrepreneurial orientation (X1)	X1.1	0.473	0.809
	X1.2	0.384	
	X1.3	0.446	
	X1.4	0.576	
	X1.5	0.422	
	X1.6	0.446	
	X1.7	0.419	
	X1.8	0.385	
	X1.9	0.402	
	X1.10	0.396	
	X1.11	0.409	
	X1.12	0.365	

	X1.13	0.350	
	X1.14	0.345	
	X1.15	0.476	
Market orientation (X2)	X2.1	0.354	0.796
	X2.2	0.498	
	X2.3	0.462	
	X2.4	0.485	
	X2.5	0.341	
	X2.6	0.444	
	X2.7	0.460	
	X2.8	0.455	
	X2.9	0.475	
	X2.10	0.464	
	X2.11	0.239	
	X2.12	0.283	
	X2.13	0.356	
	X2.14	0.468	
Competitive advantage (Y)	Y1	0.409	0.818
	Y2	0.508	
	Y3	0.483	
	Y4	0.379	
	Y5	0.531	
	Y6	0.515	
	Y7	0.408	
	Y8	0.452	
	Y9	0.424	
	Y10	0.455	
	Y11	0.306	
	Y12	0.392	
	Y13	0.374	
	Y14	0.323	
	Y15	0.548	

Source: Author's findings, 2024.

Based on Table 1 above, it can be seen that all indicators in each construct (entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, and competitive advantage) have a corrected item-total correlation value that is greater than the r-table value (0.197). This shows that all indicators are feasible and valid to be used as measurements of the constructs concerned.

Furthermore, the alpha coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) for each construct was also obtained. The results show that the alpha value is above 0.60, namely 0.809 for entrepreneurial orientation, 0.796 for market orientation, and 0.818 for competitive advantage. Therefore, the variables or constructs in this study can be said to be reliable or have a high level of reliability, indicating the accuracy of the instrument as a research variable.

With the results of this validity and reliability test, it can be ascertained that the instrument used in this study has sufficient validity and accuracy to measure the constructs of entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, and competitive advantage in creative industry MSMEs in Makassar City in the era of Revolution 5.0.

2. Path analysis results

In this study, the researcher used path analysis to see the influence of entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation on competitive advantage both directly and through market orientation as a mediating variable. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS software version 25. Path analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression analysis, where regression is performed twice. The first regression is used to measure the strength of the influence of the independent variable on the intervening variable, while the second regression is used to measure the strength of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

The following are the results of the path analysis obtained from the calculations and values on the path equation I and path equation II analysis in Table 2:

Table 2: Path analysis results

Variable	Coefficient	t	Sig.	Descriptions
Constant	11.813	3.540	-	-
Entrepreneurial orientation toward market orientation	0.815	13.926	0.000	Significant
Entrepreneurial orientation towards competitive advantage	0.479	4.829	0.000	Significant
Market orientation towards competitive advantage	0.385	3.884	0.000	Significant
Adjusted R ² model 1	0.661	-	-	-
Adjusted R ² model 2	0.673	-	-	-
Entrepreneurial orientation towards competitive advantage through market orientation	5.382			Significant

Source: Author's findings, 2024.

Based on the path analysis in the table above, it was found that the entrepreneurial orientation variable (X1) has a significant influence on market orientation with a Sig. value of 0.000. When compared with the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the Sig. value $< \alpha$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that entrepreneurial orientation affects market orientation. Furthermore, in the path analysis of equation II, it was found that the entrepreneurial orientation variable (X1) also has a significant influence on competitive advantage with a Sig. value of 0.000.

When compared with the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the Sig. value $< \alpha$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that entrepreneurial orientation affects competitive advantage. In addition, the market orientation variable (X2) also has a significant influence on competitive advantage with a Sig. value of 0.000. When compared with the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the Sig. value $< \alpha$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), indicating that market orientation affects competitive advantage.

Before calculating the significance of the mediation effect, a regression of the independent variable (X1) against the mediation variable (X2) was carried out to produce coefficient a, and a regression of the mediation variable (X2) against the dependent variable (Y) to produce coefficient b. The results show that the t-value is 5.382, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.660. Because the t-value is greater than the t-table, it can be concluded that the market

orientation variable mediates the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage. Based on the results of this path analysis, it can be concluded that entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation have a significant effect on competitive advantage in creative industry MSMEs in Makassar City in the era of Revolution 5.0. In addition, market orientation also acts as a mediating variable between entrepreneurial orientation and competitive advantage.

3. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data analysis in this study conducted related to entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation towards the competitive advantage of creative industry MSMEs in the era of the 5.0 revolution in Makassar City. The main findings obtained provide in-depth insight into the complex relationship between the influence of entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation on competitive advantage, as well as the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage through market orientation as a mediator in the creative industry sector in Makassar City.

3.1. The influence of entrepreneurial orientation on market orientation

In this study, it was found that entrepreneurial orientation has a significant impact on market orientation. This reflects how important the entrepreneurial aspect is in shaping MSME actors' understanding of rapidly changing market demands. Entrepreneurs who have a strong entrepreneurial orientation tend to be better able to respond to changing trends and consumer needs, creating a strong foundation for innovation and adaptation.

The results of data processing show that the significance value (Sig.) of the influence of the entrepreneurial orientation variable on market orientation is 0.000, with a beta coefficient value of 0.815. This shows that this influence is acceptable based on the established significance criteria. In this context, previous studies also support this finding by showing that entrepreneurial orientation affects market orientation (Karim et al, 2023). A proactive attitude towards change and an innovative culture are important factors in creating new products that can meet consumer needs. MSME actors with a strong entrepreneurial orientation tend to create innovative products and respond to changing trends in the market so that they can meet consumer needs (Fitriani & Zaenal, 2023).

3.2. The influence of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage

The results of this study indicate that entrepreneurial orientation has also been proven to have a positive effect on competitive advantage. MSME actors who have high entrepreneurial initiatives tend to create products or services with better quality and uniqueness compared to their competitors. This confirms the strategic role of entrepreneurial orientation in achieving competitive advantage (Abduh et al, 2023). The results of data processing show that the significance value (Sig.) between the entrepreneurial orientation variable and competitive advantage is 0.000 with a beta coefficient of 0.479. This finding indicates that the influence of the entrepreneurial orientation variable on competitive advantage can be accepted significantly.

In competition in the handicraft MSME sector, the proactive attitude and innovative behaviour of business actors can increase competitive advantage. Creative strategies and successful product innovations can win the competition and create customer satisfaction, which in turn increases the number of customers and competitive advantage (Kurniawan & Althalets, 2024). MSME actors with a strong entrepreneurial orientation tend to have a proactive attitude, innovate, and create superior products that differentiate them from their competitors.

3.3. The influence of market orientation on competitive advantage

In this study, it was found that market orientation also has a significant influence on competitive advantage. The better the market orientation of MSMEs, the better their competitive advantage. MSMEs who can read and understand market dynamics well have an advantage in creating products that are according to consumer preferences. Good market orientation is correlated with the ability to identify opportunities, anticipate changing trends, and quickly adjust business strategies (Salim et al, 2024). The results of data processing show that the significance value (Sig.) between the market orientation variable and competitive advantage is 0.000 with a beta coefficient of 0.385.

This finding confirms that market orientation plays an important role in creating a competitive advantage. This finding is in line with previous research showing that market orientation affects competitive advantage and allows MSMEs to determine trends and present product variations and prices that follow market demand. MSMEs need to continue to pay attention to changes in the market and be responsive to these changes to create innovative products that meet consumer needs.

3.4. The influence of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage through market orientation

The results of the path analysis show that market orientation acts as a mediating variable between entrepreneurial orientation and competitive advantage. In other words, market orientation mediates the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage. This finding suggests that a deep understanding of the market can be a major driver in bridging entrepreneurial efforts and competitive advantage outcomes. The calculation results show that the t-value (5.382) is greater than the t-table value (1.660), indicating that market orientation is proven to mediate the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage. This supports the findings of previous studies which found that market orientation has an important role in linking entrepreneurial orientation with competitive advantage.

Overall, these findings provide an in-depth understanding of the complexity of interrelated factors in the context of creative industry MSMEs in the era of Revolution 5.0, providing a strong foundation for developing better and more sustainable business strategies in the future. A market that is approached with a good market orientation will be able to create a sustainable competitive advantage. The proactive attitude of MSME actors in creating products and following market trends by being responsive to customer and competitor demands will bring a competitive advantage to the company (Karim & Syamsuddin, 2024). A strong entrepreneurial orientation in assessing customer needs and creating innovative products also plays an

important role in increasing competitive advantage. The research focused on entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, and competitive advantage of creative industry MSMEs in the era of Revolution 5.0 in Makassar City provides a clear picture of the transformation of the handicraft industry. Despite its traditional roots, this industry can utilize technological innovation wisely, opening up opportunities for craftsmen to combine local wisdom with modern production methods. Technology integration opens the door to the development of higher creativity, increasing competitiveness, and expanding the reach of product distribution, allowing craft products to be more affordable and known in a wider market.

The results of this study indicate that entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation influence the competitive advantage of MSMEs in the Handicraft and Culinary sectors in Makassar City. Strong entrepreneurial orientation encourages MSMEs to innovate, be responsive to market changes, and create superior products. In addition, good market orientation allows MSMEs to identify consumer needs, adjust products to market trends, and meet customer needs well. In the context of tight competition, MSMEs with good entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation have a higher competitive advantage.

In the context of MSMEs in the Handicraft and Culinary sectors, business actors need to explore information about the background and characteristics of customers and developing trends. By focusing on consumer needs, MSMEs can formulate the right strategy for creating superior and innovative products. In addition, market orientation also allows MSMEs to determine product variations, determine appropriate prices, and increase customer satisfaction. To achieve competitive advantage, MSMEs also need to be careful in managing risks that may arise. Strict evaluation of products and observation of market changes are important in creating unique products that have advantages over competitors (Wahyuni et al, 2022). Proactive entrepreneurial orientation, the ability to see market opportunities, and product innovation are the keys to creating sustainable competitive advantage.

This finding can contribute to the understanding of the importance of entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation in increasing the competitive advantage of MSMEs in the creative industry in Makassar City in the era of Revolution 5.0. The practical implication of this study is the need for MSME actors to develop entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation as strategies to increase competitive advantage. This study can also be a basis for the government and related stakeholders in formulating policies that support the development of MSMEs in the creative industry in Makassar City.

CONCLUSION

The realization of partner collaboration in research on entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation towards the competitive advantage of creative industry MSMEs in the era of the 5.0 revolution in Makassar City greatly contributed to the smoothness and relevance of the research. The following are some realizations of partner involvement. Creative industry players, such as MSME owners, business managers, or practitioners in Makassar City, were invited for interviews. They shared valuable experiences, views, and input regarding entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, and the challenges they face in the era of the

5.0 revolution. This provides a relevant practical perspective for research. Creative industry partners became respondents in surveys or questionnaires used in the research. Their data provides very important information about entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, and business practices in the creative industry. Creative industry partners collaborated in collecting primary data, such as collecting sales data, consumer data, or other operational data. This facilitates more accurate and comprehensive data collection. After the research was completed, creative industry partners were invited to validate the research results. They provided input and further understanding of the relevance of the research results in a practical context. Creative industry partners are also involved in research dissemination efforts, such as participating in seminars, workshops, or joint publications. This greatly helps disseminate research findings to the business and industry community.

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